

Isolation and identification of galactose utilizing bacteria from *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*

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Abstract

Galactose is an intriguing organic compound for its structural similarity to glucose and unique chemical activity. Whereas human cells are suited to consume glucose, they are unable to live on galactose due to the lower metabolic efficiency from the inability to provoke rapid ATP production. In this study, I isolated bacteria from samples collected from Dapeng Bay (22.55°N, 114.47°E), Longhua *Litopenaeus vannamei* hatcheries (22.76°N, 114.04°E), and the giant freshwater prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*, and I cultivated them in different media for purposes of comparison. Upon the completion of at least two rounds of purification and then DNA sequencing, *Halomonas litopenaei* was isolated from a *Litopenaeus vannamei* water sample growing on Marine Agar 2216, and *Mesorhizobium sediminum* was isolated from a seawater sample growing on Marine Agar 2216.

1. Introduction

Galactose is rarely found as a free carbon source in nature, but it is also one of the most abundant sugars in the human diet. Galactose is commonly combined with other monosaccharides to form lactose or complex carbohydrates like glycolipids, so these glycoconjugates fulfill various biological functions. So far, Galactosemia, six congenital disorders of glycosylation (CDGs), and five lysosomal storage diseases (LSDs) have been proven to be linked to galactose metabolism [1]. Increased understanding of the influences of galactose is important to better mediate disorders linked to galactose homeostasis. Once explored, its potential for therapeutic applications can be realized. Moreover, galactose provides a lens into evolution and genetic variation. The enzymatic products of genes *GALK*, *GALT*, *GALM*, and *GALE* in humans are responsible for converting galactose into glucose-1-phosphate [2]. The Leloir galactose utilization of budding yeasts has been established as a model system for understanding the evolution of eukaryotic metabolic pathways and their regulation [3]. Little selec-

tion has been conducted for galactose-utilizing bacteria, and the research into the effects of galactose on the aforementioned grounds is relatively new. Hence, this setup proves intriguing as a potential answer to a 'black box' scenario due to the fact that galactose is associated with the aforementioned new discoveries and that most organisms are unable to survive solely on it. Similarly, the oceans remain unexplored, and the same can be said for marine bacteria. The remaining 99% have not yet been cultured [4]. As a fulfillment of research gaps in both areas, I sampled water from both Dapeng Bay and *Litopenaeus vannamei* hatcheries and digestive organs from the *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* shrimp. I designed the selective LB-G medium to investigate the bacterium that can thrive with only galactose as its source of carbohydrates. I also prepared Marine Agar 2216 medium to grow marine bacteria. After that, I extracted the bacterial DNA and identified the cultivated bacterium.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection of Samples

Sea water samples were collected in Shenzhen Dapeng Bay, and *Litopenaeus vannamei* water samples were collected from hatcheries in Longhua located in Guangdong, China. The samples were collected by hand. The water samples were collected by dipping the medium below surface level whereas the *Litopenaeus vannamei* pond wastewater was a fast glide at the face of the water. Shrimp samples were *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* purchased online and dissected in the laboratory to extract the blood, intestines, and stomach glands.

Received: 19 November 2024 Accepted: 25 December 2024

Published: 25 January 2025

Citation: Liu, L. (2025). Isolation and identification of galactose-utilizing bacteria from *Macrobrachium rosenbergii*. The Young Scientist, 4(1), 79-85.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14739705>

2.2. Preparation of Samples

The samples of *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* blood, intestines, and stomach glands were prepared for inoculation in the lab. The body parts were separated into three test tubes, each filled with 1000 μL of purified water. A vibrating pen is required to grind each sample thoroughly until it reaches a semblance of a homogeneous mixture. The vibrating pen must be washed between usages. After appropriate mixing, the samples were put in the centrifuge for five minutes at 1500 rpm and stored upright in a 4°C incubator. The water samples include that of the sponge, regular Dapeng seawater, *Litopenaeus vannamei* hatchery, and wastewater of the *Litopenaeus vannamei* hatchery. These samples were directly diluted in the biosafety cabinet along with the centrifuged *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* samples. Before inoculation, the *Litopenaeus vannamei* water samples were diluted one hundred times and one thousand times; the *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* samples were diluted ten times and one hundred times; the Dapeng seawater was diluted one thousand times.

2.3. Spreading and Streaking

After the preparation and dilution of the used samples, spreading rods were used to spread the samples onto the respective mediums. The regular seawater samples used only the Marine Agar 2216 (as "2216" hereafter) plates, producing two plates. The marine sponge, *Litopenaeus vannamei* hatchery, and wastewater samples were inoculated onto LB Agar and LB-Galactose Agar, which is a selective medium that replaces the yeast extract in LB Agar with the carbohydrate, galactose. These samples would produce six plates. The *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* samples were inoculated onto LB Agar and LB-G Agar as well. They were then incubated at 28 degrees Celsius and checked on every following day.

2.4. DNA Extraction

The water bath method was used for DNA extraction. After two to three purification attempts that had rendered the bacterium pure, a positive displacement pipette with a 10 μL micro tip was dipped into the single bacterial colony for every dish. The pipette was dipped into 100 μL of purified water in a test tube. This process was repeated seven times for each bacterium. These test tubes were then placed in the water bath floating racks and boiled in the thermostat water bath at 100°C for 10 minutes. Afterward, the test tubes were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes.

2.5. Running PCR

The solution used for the PCR test included 1 μL of DNA primers 27F (5'-AGAGTTTGATCCTGGCTCAG-3') and 1492R (5'-GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3'), 12.5 μL of Taq polymerase, 7.5 μL of double distilled water, and 3

μL of DNA contents. This was made for each bacterium. The PCR machine was set to run a program including the steps: 95°C for three minutes, followed by a cycle repeated 32 times, including 30 seconds with a temperature of 95°C and 20 seconds at 55°C. The cycle was continued for 8 minutes at 72°C and then ended at 4°C for solution preservation.

2.6. Electrophoresis Test

The solutions will then go through gel electrophoresis to determine if DNA was successfully extracted. The preparation for the gel test includes agarose powder, TAE buffer, and nucleic acid dye. 1.2 g of agarose powder was added to 80 mL of TAE buffer and 4 μL of nucleic acid dye. The solution was then poured into the agarose gel mold for 30 minutes. After the gel solidified, 5 μL of each PCR product was injected into separate rectangular spaces in the gel, with the first space loaded with 5 μL of DNA marker. The machine ran for 20 minutes at 120 V of voltage.

2.7. DNA Sequencing

The three tubes that were successfully identified in the PCR test were then sent to the Tsingke Biotech Company for DNA Sanger sequencing. The sequencing data was processed by converting the file of genetic information through the MEGA 7 application into FASTA form. To determine the identity of the sequence, the sequenced 16S rDNA fragments had gone through the process of nucleotide blast (blastn against NCBI nucleotide (nt) database), and the result with the highest percentage of identity and the lowest error value would be taken as the species ID.

3. Results

3.1. Bacterial inoculation of blood samples

From *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* blood samples, bacterial inoculation was performed, with a ten times and one hundred times dilution on each sample with an LB medium. Based on observations, for the LB blood 10x dilution sample there were at least 3 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with light yellow color, circular form, small size, and raised morphology; pinkish white color, irregular form, and raised morphology; and pale white color, circular form, and umbonate morphology. For the LB blood 100x dilution sample, there were at least 4 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with a pronounced yellow color, round form, small size, and convex morphology; pinkish white color, irregular form, and raised morphology. For the LB-G blood 100x dilution sample, there were at least two different types of observable colonies: one with a yellowish color, irregular form, and raised morphology. Another with pale white color, round form, and flat morphology (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Bacterial inoculation of blood, stomach, and intestine samples using different medium plates

3.2. Bacterial inoculation of stomach samples

Further bacterial inoculation was performed for *Macrobacterium rosenbergii* stomach samples, with a ten times

and one hundred times dilution on each sample with an LB medium. Based on observations, for the LB stomach 10x dilution sample there were at least 3 different types of ob-

Figure 2: Bacterial inoculation of Dapeng seawater samples in 2216 medium plates

servable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with pale white color, circular form, small size, and raised morphology; beige color, irregular form, small size, and raised morphology; and greenish color, circular form, small size, and raised morphology. For the LB stomach 100x dilution sample, there were at least 5 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with a pale translucent appearance, irregular form, and flat morphology; pinkish beige color, round form, and raised morphology; brownish green color, irregular form, and umbonate morphology; greenish translucent color, round form, and raised morphology; and white opaque color, round form, small size, and raised morphology. For the LB-G stomach 100x dilution sample, there were at least two different types of observable colonies: one with white color, irregular form, undulated edges, and raised morphology. Another with pale white color, round form, small size, and raised morphology (Fig.1).

3.3. Bacterial inoculation of intestine samples

Final processes for bacterial inoculation were performed for *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* intestine samples, with a ten times and one hundred times dilution on each sample with an LB medium. Based on observations, for the LB intestine 10x dilution sample, there were at least 4 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with pale white opaque color, circular form, small size, and raised morphology; white translucent color, round form, and flat morphology; light beige color, irregular form, and raised morphology; and yellowish color, irregular form, and raised morphology. For the LB intestine 100x

dilution sample, there were at least 4 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with a white opaque appearance, round form, small size, and raised morphology; pronounced yellow color, round form, and umbonate morphology; light beige color, round form, and flat morphology; and greenish translucent color, round form, and flat morphology. For the LB-G intestine 100x dilution sample, there were at least two different types of observable colonies: one with a white translucent color, round form, and flat morphology. Another with an opaque beige color, irregular form, undulated edges, and raised morphology (Fig.1).

3.4. Bacterial inoculation of Dapeng seawater

From Dapeng seawater samples, bacterial inoculation was also performed, with one thousand times dilution for both 2216 plates. Based on observations, for the 2216 plate I, there were at least 4 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with saturated yellow color, circular form, undulated edges, and flat morphology; pink color, circular form, and flat morphology; beige color, circular form, and raised morphology; and green color, circular form, curled margins, and flat morphology. For the second 2216 plate II, there were at least 4 different types of observable bacterial colonies. Example colonies include those with a pronounced yellow color, irregular form, varied size, and raised morphology; pinkish white color, circular form, and raised morphology; green color, irregular form, and curled margins; and white color, circular form, small size, and raised morphology (Fig.2).

Figure 3: Bacterial purification of LB Blood 10x, 2216 *Litopenaeus vannamei* water, and LB-G Stomach 100x bacterial colonies

Figure 4: Bacterial purification of LB Blood 10x, 2216 sea water, and LB *Litopenaeus vannamei* water bacterial colonies

Figure 5: Bacterial purification of 2216 *Litopenaeus vannamei* water, LB Blood 100x, and LB-G Stomach 100x bacterial colonies

Figure 6: Bacterial purification of a 2216 seawater bacterial colony

3.5. Bacterial isolation and identification

In the end, ten bacterium were purified enough to send to PCR (Fig.3) (Fig.4) (Fig.5) (Fig.6). Out of these sam-

Figure 7: PCR results for the first seven isolates

ples, two of them were able to be identified with the current methodology of water bath for DNA extraction (Fig.7) (Fig.8). Upon DNA sequencing, the identified 2216 *Litopenaeus vannamei* water bacterium Sample B was classified as *Halomonas litopenaei* species with 99.88 percent genetic similarity. The identified 2216 seawater bacterium Sample J would be the *Mesorhizobium sediminum* with 100.00 percent genetic similarity.

4. Discussion

4.1. *Halomonas litopenaei*

The *Halomonas litopenaei* is a halophilic and exopolysaccharide-producing bacterium [5]. It belongs to the genus *Halomonas* which is part of the family *Halomonadaceae* in the class *Gammaproteobacteria* [6]. Its cells are Gram-stain-negative and aerobic in the shape of short rods and are moderately halophilic. It is unsurprising to isolate the *Halomonas litopenaei* from the *Litopenaeus vannamei* water sample, as the inhabiting shrimp is the *Litopenaeus vannamei* species from which the *Halomonas litopenaei* was first discovered and named after, and it was raised in the 2216 medium that simulates the ocean, explaining its salinity tolerance. Due to its halophilic tendencies, it could be grown on a medium simulating the environment of the ocean. The bacteria possess complete or truncated denitrification pathways that are likely serving a role in the *Litopenaeus vannamei* freshwater to convert methane into carbon dioxide, water, and energy, improving

Figure 8: PCR results for the last three isolates

water quality [7]. Moreover, the secondary metabolites of the *Halomonas litopenaei* could be a source for the synthesis of antimicrobial compounds, preservatives, and a promising field for drug discovery and development. However, more research is needed to fully explore its potential clinical and therapeutic uses [8].

4.2. *Mesorhizobium sediminum*

The bacteria species *Mesorhizobium sediminum* is a gram-staining-negative, short rod, non-motile, non-spore-forming, aerobic bacterium [9]. It belongs to the genus *Mesorhizobium* and is a member of the family *Phyllobacteriaceae*. The first incidence of *Mesorhizobium sediminum* was isolated from deep-sea sediment collected from the Indian Ocean, so it is reasonable to isolate the *Mesorhizobium sediminum* from the Dapeng seawater sample due to the similarity of the environments from which it was sampled and that it had been grown in a medium simulating marine habitats. The *Mesorhizobium sediminum* can act as a source of biofertilizers in agriculture with the precedent of the activity of other plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria, closely related to the *Mesorhizobium* genus, that either provide nutrients and regulate plant growth or protect plants from acquiring infections [10]. Hence, it has a beneficial association with sustainable agriculture [11].

4.3. Experience from DNA extraction of the isolated bacteria

For both bacteria, DNA extraction succeeded through the water boiling method due to both bacteria being gram-negative. Hence, it is likely that the five other bacteria were gram-positive, so the DNA, impeded by thicker layers of peptidoglycan, could not be extracted. Nevertheless, the bacterium growing on the LB-Galactose petri dishes could not be identified by the current methods. Therefore, more can be done for the identification process with reagent test kits. As for the methods of cultivation, they may play a role in influencing the results as well since the mediums only offer a narrow simulation of the original habitats of the respective bacterium. With a limited amount of nutrients available, the mediums may have gotten rid of bacterium reliant on other combinations, resulting in their ultimate absence.

5. Conclusion

Ten purified bacterial plates underwent DNA extraction and received PCR, and two were identified: *Halomonas litopenaei* as a *Litopenaeus vannamei* water sample raised in a 2216 medium and *Mesorhizobium sediminum* as a marine water sample raised in a 2216 medium. *Halomonas litopenaei* is a halophilic bacterium that is significant for its production of secondary metabolites. It demonstrates potential in clinical and therapeutic contexts as an actor in synthesizing antimicrobial compounds. *Mesorhizobium sediminum* is an aerobic marine bacterium that is suggested to have nitrogen-fixing properties. It demonstrates potential in sustainable agriculture, but this genus is a highly under-researched area. More potential uses and likely indicators about the environment it is found in can only be uncovered with substantial research into its role in the marine habitat. The main objective of this study was not met, but further experimentation could be conducted to identify the eight other purified bacteria and gain an understanding of the effect of galactose over bacterial populations and the indications of a bacterium capable of utilization to better access the uses of galactose in medicine and evolutionary tracing.

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